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List of Abbreviations

AFQ	Accelerated Fuel Qualification
AOO	Anticipated Operational Occurrence
ATF	Accident Tolerant Fuel
DBA	Design Beyond Accident
DOE	Department of Energy
GFR	Gas-cooled Fast Reactor
FIMA	Fissions per Initial Metal Atom
FPC	Fuel Performance Code
HTGR	High Temperature Gas-cooled Reactor
HTR	High Temperature Reactor
HWR	Heavy Water Reactor
LFR	Lead Fast Reactor
LOCA	Loss-Of Coolant Accident
LWR	Light Water Reactor
MA	Minor Actinide
MOX	Mixed Oxide
MSR	Molten Salt Reactor
MTR	Materials Testing Reactor
NEA	Nuclear Energy Agency
PCI	Pellet-Cladding Interaction
PHWR	Pressurized Heavy Water Reactor
PIE	Post Irradiation Examination
PIRT	Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table Method
RIA	Reactivity Insertion Accidents
SCWR	Super-Critical Water Reactor
SFR	Sodium Fast Reactor
TRISO	TRI-structural ISOTropic
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
US NRC	US Nuclear Regulatory Commission
VHTR	Very High Temperature Reactor

Summary

This document is the report regarding the subtask “6.4.3 Overview of testing procedures for the characterization of innovative fuels” which is the part of the pre-selected project “6.4 Preliminary analysis of the requirements for selected test-beds for nuclear materials” related to the Work Package 6 of the CONNECT-NM Partnership.

The report deals with requirements and objectives of irradiations of candidate fuels, and lists available neutron and ion irradiation facilities together with their operational capabilities and restrictions.

The report suggests that in order to accelerate fuel development, fuel system phenomena, properties, and parameters must be prioritized in respect to both the significance and the knowledge gaps of them. This can be identified by a phenomena identification and ranking table exercise on any innovative fuel. Then, depending of the required fuel properties and fuel maturity, i.e. fuel technical readiness level, the fuel qualification programme can be formalized in details to close knowledge gaps.

The report is structured in accordance with the Work Package Work Plan outlined in the Annex I to the CONNECT-NM Grant Agreement.

1. Introduction

This document is the internal deliverable 6.4.3 entitled “*User requirement specifications for irradiation testing of innovative fuels, including candidate (ion and neutron) irradiation facilities*” which is the part of the pre-selected project “6.4 Preliminary analysis of the requirements for selected test-beds for nuclear materials” related to the Work Package 6 of the CONNECT-NM Partnership. This subtask was carried out from October 2024 until January 2026.

The purpose of this document is to define the user requirements for conducting irradiation testing of innovative nuclear fuel concepts in materials testing reactors (MTRs) and ion irradiation facilities (accelerated damage simulation). The innovative nuclear fuels are considered such as advanced ceramic fuels, composite fuels, accident-tolerant fuels (ATFs), and high burnup fuel concepts. The irradiation testing is crucial for validating fuel behaviour under representative reactor conditions to support qualification, licensing, and eventual commercial deployment.

In addition, the report gives an overview of available MTRs and ion accelerators in the world together with their operational capabilities and restrictions.

2. Innovative nuclear fuels

The development of nuclear fuel around the world has been going on for such a long time, even before the first installation of the nuclear power plant. These developments are carried out in order to increase the safety and provide better performance fuel leading to safer and more efficient nuclear power plant. Furthermore, with the current needs to have more reliable energy production, the development and improvement of the nuclear fuel becomes more imminent.

Innovative nuclear fuel (or advanced nuclear fuel) refers to new or improved types of fuel designed to make nuclear reactors safer, more efficient, and more sustainable compared to conventional uranium oxide (UO₂) fuel used in today’s light-water reactors. In more details, innovative nuclear fuels aim to:

- increase efficiency: extract more energy from each unit of uranium;
- enhance safety: withstand higher temperatures and reduce the chance of accidents,
- reduce waste: produce less long-lived radioactive waste or enable recycling,
- support advanced reactors: enable new reactor types (like fast reactors or molten salt reactors).

A brief overview of the fuel materials for the current and next generation nuclear systems was published under the ORIENT-NM project [1]. In general, innovative nuclear fuels can be classified in two groups:

- Accident-Tolerant Fuels (ATFs) designed for existing light-water reactors (LWRs) to improve performance and safety under accident conditions (Table 1), and
- Advanced Reactor Fuels, developed for Gen IV and non-LWR designs (Table 2).

As regards to the ATFs, the qualification of fuel and/or cladding is required to bring a certain fuel concept as a whole to a higher maturity level. For example, UO₂ fuel and UO₂

fuel with additives (Cr_2O_3 , Al_2O_3) has a high maturity level but the introduction of coated cladding requires additional integral qualification testing in respect to a pellet-cladding interaction and behaviour under accident conditions to demonstrate advantages of a new fuel concept.

Table 1. Examples of accident-tolerant fuels.

Fuel Material	Cladding Material	Benefits
U_3Si_2	FeCrAl-ODS	Higher uranium density, better thermal conductivity
UO_2	Chromium-coated Zr-based alloys	Delays oxidation, improves safety margins
UO_2 with additives (Cr_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 , etc.)	Standard Zr-based alloy or coated	Improved fission gas retention, reduced swelling
UO_2 or U_3Si_2	SiC/SiC composite	High temperature tolerance, corrosion resistance
U-Mo alloy	Advanced Zr-based alloy or coated	High density, good stability.

Table 2. Examples of advanced reactor fuels.

Type	Description	Benefits
TRISO fuels (Tri-structural Isotropic)	Used in High-Temperature Gas Reactors (HTGRs), Microreactors. Uranium oxycarbide (UCO) or uranium dioxide (UO_2) kernel coated with carbon and SiC layers.	Extremely robust, can operate at very high temperatures.
Metallic fuels (e.g., U-Zr, U-Pu-Zr, U-Mo)	Used in fast reactors, sodium-cooled or lead-cooled systems	High thermal conductivity, breeding potential, compact core designs
Molten Salt Fuels (e.g., UF_4 or ThF_4 dissolved in molten LiF-BeF ₂)	Used in Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs)	Excellent heat transfer, potential for online reprocessing.
Nitride fuels	Used in fast or advanced reactors	High thermal conductivity, dense fuel form, less fission gas release
Thorium-based fuels (ThO_2 - UO_2 , ThO_2 - U_3Si_2 , Th-U mixed nitride)	Used in thermal or molten salt reactors	Abundant thorium, lower transuranic waste, breeding of ^{233}U
Minor actinides bearing fuels	Envisaged use for recycling in PWRs, prospective for use in all fast reactors	Afterburning of minor actinides should reduce the amount of nuclear waste and its radioactivity

2.1 Technology readiness levels for nuclear fuels

Advanced nuclear fuels and materials development is a critical technology needed for closing the nuclear fuel cycle. Because the deployment of a new nuclear fuel form requires a lengthy and expensive research, development, and demonstration program, applying the Technical Readiness Level (TRL) concept to the advanced fuel development program is very useful as a management and tracking tool. Technical readiness levels are measures used to evaluate the technical maturity of evolving technologies during development. For determining the appropriate TRL for advanced nuclear fuels there are two elements used to evaluate the maturity of a new fuel type in terms of readiness for deployment [2]:

- Process Maturity, which measures how well the fabrication process is understood and validated.
- Fuel Performance Maturity, which measures how well the in-pile performance of the fuel is understood and validated.

A TRL definition that provides a balance between these two elements is essential. Testing a very mature fabrication process at very large scales for fuels with large uncertainties in its performance would not be effective. On the other hand, collecting performance data through large-scale testing without a mature definition of the fabrication process is equally unbalanced.

The definition and assessment of TRLs are part of an overall process for performing a technology readiness assessment process. The process provides information regarding the state of technology development as well as the required research and development to bring a technology to a desired level of maturity. The TRL definitions for advanced nuclear fuels either in use today or currently under development are summarized in [Table 3](#) [2]. The TRLs are divided into three major functional categories or phases; TRL 1–3: Proof-of-Concept, TRL 4–6: Proof-of-Principle, and TRL 7–9: Proof-of-Performance. All the criteria in a given level must be completed before the critical technology elements are considered achieving that level designation.

The TRL assessment for various advanced nuclear fuels have been performed and published elsewhere [2] [3]. A comprehensive summary of an international best case scenario for each technology with the TRL being representative of its most developed form in the country or countries is given in [Table 4](#) [3]. [Table 4](#) also considers TRLs with respect to the reactor type(s) for which the fuel concept is most developed. A lower TRL may apply to the use of the same fuel concept in a different reactor type. TRLs with respect to reactor type are given in [Table 5](#).

Table 3. TRL definitions for advanced nuclear fuels development [2].

TRL functions		Definitions
1	Proof-of-concept	A new concept is proposed. Technical options for the concept are identified and relevant literature data reviewed. Criteria developed.
2		Technical options are ranked. Performance range and fabrication process parametric ranges defined based on analyses.
3		Concepts are verified through laboratory-scale experiments and characterization. Fabrication process verified using surrogates.
4	Proof-of-principle	Fabrication of samples using stockpile materials at bench-scale irradiation testing of small-samples (rodlets) in relevant environment. Design parameters and features established. Basic properties compiled.
5		Fabrication of pins using prototypic feedstock materials at laboratory-scale. Pin-scale irradiation testing at relevant environment. Primary performance parameters with representative compositions under normal operating conditions quantified. Fuel behaviour models developed for use in fuel performance code(s).
6		Fabrication of pins using prototypic feedstock materials at laboratory-scale and using prototypic fabrication processes. Pin-scale irradiation testing at relevant and prototypic environment (steady state and transient testing). Predictive fuel performance code(s) and safety basis establishment.
7	Proof-of-performance	Fabrication of test assemblies using prototypic feedstock materials at engineering-scale and using prototypic fabrication processes. Assembly-scale irradiation testing in prototypic environment. Predictive fuel performance code(s) validated. Safety basis established for full-core operations.
8		Fabrication of a few core-loads of fuel and operation of a prototype reactor with such fuel.
9		Routine commercial-scale operations. Multiple reactors operating.

Table 4. Summary of the advanced fuels including their best case TRL [3].

Fuel categories		Best case TRL	Remarks
Oxide Fuel	UO ₂	9*	Vast majority of fuel has been used in almost all commercial reactors worldwide for decades [4].
	MOX (<12% PuO ₂)	9*	Used in many commercial LWRs [4].
	Advanced UO ₂	9	Commercially produced by AREVA (Cr ₂ O ₃) and Westinghouse (Cr ₂ O ₃ -Al ₂ O ₃) [4].
	Advanced MOX	9	High PuO ₂ content MOX used in commercial scale SFR in Russia [4].
	ThO ₂	8	A significant amount of thorium bearing fuels has been irradiated in commercial PHWRs in India [5].
	Minor Actinides (MAs)	4	A number of irradiation tests of MA fuels have been conducted for SFR applications [6].
Metallic	Advanced Metal	7	Hundreds of U-Pu-Zr fuel rods have been irradiated in prototype SFR in the USA [6].
Ceramic Fuel	Zirconium hydride-based	6	Commonly used in TRIGA research reactor with concept development for LWRs [7].
	Carbide (U,Pu)C	7	Manufactured and irradiated in a prototype scale SFR in India [8].
	Uranium Nitride (UN)	7	Manufactured and irradiated in a prototype scale SFR in Russia [9].
	Uranium Silicide (U ₂ Si ₃)	4	LWR rodlet irradiation programme by Westinghouse-led consortium [10].
	Coated particle	7	Significant manufacturing and irradiation experience for prototype HTGRs [11]. Commercial operation of a high-temperature gas-cooled pebble-bed reactor HTR-PM in China since 2023.
Liquid-based	Molten salt	4	Experience of the use of U-based molten salts fuels in test reactors in the USA in the 1950s and 1960s [12].

* The TRL level is reduced from 10 to 9 as the highest TRL level is widely accepted to be 9.

Table 5. TRLs of innovative fuels based on the nuclear technologies [3].

Fuel	Estimated TRL							
	Gen III		Gen IV					
	LWR	HWR	SFR	GFR	LFR	MSR	HTR/ VHTR	SCWR
UO ₂	9 ^a	9 ^a	-	-	-	-	7	3
MOX (<12% PuO ₂)	9 ^a	9 ^a	-	-	-	-	4	2
Cr ₂ O ₃ and Al ₂ O ₃ doped UO ₂	9	-	-	-	-	-	2	2
Nb ₂ O ₃ doped UO ₂	7	-	-	-	-	-	2	2
High Gd ₂ O ₃ doped UO ₂	2	-	-	-	-	-	2	2
UO ₂ annular pellets	7 ^b	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Advanced MOX	7	2 ^c	-	9	3	4	-	2
Cr ₂ O ₃ doped MOX	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Thorium-contained	5	8 ^d	4	1	2	4	6	2
Minor Actinides	4	-	4	2	3	2	2	2
Advanced metal	4	-	7	1	4	-	-	1
Zr hydride-based	5	-	-	2	-	-	-	1
UC	2	-	7	3	2	-	6 ^e	1
UN	3	-	7	1	4	-	2	1
U ₂ Si ₃	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Coated particle	5	-	-	-	-	-	2-7 ^f	1
Molten salt	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	-

^a The TRL level from [3] is reduced from 10 to 9 as the highest TRL level is widely accepted to be 9.

^b TRL = 9 in VVER

^c High Pu content

^d Once through the Th-recycle

^f As UCO in coated particles

^e Depends on the kernel type

The UO₂ fuelled Zr-based alloy clad fuel system used in most light water reactors (LWR) today is clearly ranked at TRL 9. The UO₂-Zr fuel system is fabricated at commercial scale by a selection of commercial nuclear fuel vendors and is used in over 400 operating commercial reactors world-wide. The doped UO₂ fuels (e.g. Westinghouse ADOPT fuel, UO₂ doped with small amounts of Cr₂O₃ and Al₂O₃), commonly used in LWRs, also have high maturity, while some of doped UO₂ fuels still have a really low maturity like high Gd₂O₃ doped UO₂.

The high maturity of the MOX fuel is also dictated by the fact that it is used in many commercial LWRs [4]. The high TRL level for MOX fuel is also achieved for Gen IV reactors,

namely, for the sodium-cooled fast reactors (SFRs). Typically those SFRs are experimental test reactors as currently, there are only two commercial SFRs connected to the grid - both are operated in the Russian Federation (BN-600 and BN-800) using MOX fuel.

In term of the high-density fuels (nitride, silicide, carbide and metallic fuels) for LWRs, their maturity is characterized as low. While, as regards to the Gen IV technology, carbide, nitride and advanced metallic fuels for SFRs have a relatively high maturity. The GFR, MSR, (V)HTR and SCWR are unfortunately known to have a low maturity fuel [3].

In 2014, the NEA Expert Group on Innovative Fuel Elements (EGIFE) published a report on the "State-of-the-art Report on Innovative Fuels for Advanced Nuclear Systems" covering several fuel types which contains minor actinides [6]:

- metallic fuels,
- oxide fuels,
- nitride fuels,
- dispersion fuels (including ceramic-in-ceramic (CERCER) and ceramic-in-metal (CERMET) dispersions), and
- special mechanical fuel forms (particle fuels, sphere-pac, vibro-pac).

At the present time, transuranic bearing fuels are being developed only at laboratory scale and irradiation tests have been limited to small samples, rodlets and in some cases one pin. Technology readiness levels were assessed in [6] for all fuels and the results ranged from 3 for nitrides, 3-4 for dispersion fuels, and to 4-5 for oxides and metal fuels.

However, due to a continuous improvement and development, it is currently difficult to pinpoint the exact TRL maturity of each innovative fuels [3]. Furthermore, the progress of each development of each fuel is not the same. The latest TRL ranking was provided by ORIENT-NM identity cards in 2022 [13]. It can be seen that the TRLs in ORIENT-NM identity cards are not much different from those presented in [3] in spite of seven years between TRL assessments. This is a case in point that that the fuel qualification process should be accelerated to ensure faster introduction of innovative fuels in the current and next generation nuclear systems.

The TRL concept is used as a program management tool and is not meant as an absolute quantitative measure of maturity. There is naturally a level of subjectivity in defining and in evaluating the TRLs. It is important to recognize the difference between the TRL evaluations and technical risk. The TRL provides a measure of technology maturity compared to the final objective of large-scale deployment. A low TRL does not necessarily mean a high technical risk. Technical risk depends on many factors (e.g., the complexity of the remaining work, the availability of the needed resources and testing facilities, schedule constraints) and must be evaluated independently.

2.2 Fuel qualification process

The aim is to ensure that the final design meets all of the fuel design requirements and the associated limits. Fuel design qualification is achieved through analysis using qualified methods and through qualification testing.

A qualification process should rely on a systematic analysis of all available data and operational experience for identification of gaps in knowledge and potential new failure

modes. A research and development program should be employed to address gaps in knowledge. When necessary, separate effect testing and integral testing should be performed to confirm safety limits and fuel acceptance criteria. The use of demonstration irradiation or lead test assemblies in conjunction with surveillance is encouraged.

When establishing the fuel qualification process, fuel designs for advanced reactors should use appropriate international guidance, such as NUREG-2246, Fuel Qualification for Advanced Reactors [14].

2.2.1 Classical approach

The classical approach and rationale of fuel qualification process was documented in [15]. The approach was described as four phases, with emphasis on selecting a reference fuel concept, evaluating and improving the fuel to develop a fuel specification for a reference design, obtaining data to support a licensing safety case for the fuel, and final qualification of the fuel for a specific application. Because a fuel program requires long-lead-time irradiation testing, bringing a fuel design from the initial concept through licensing might take over 20 years in order to reach the high maturity for the deployment in the nuclear reactor. The TRL is used to define the maturity of nuclear fuels. This approach divides the TRL levels into several “Fuel Development Phases” (Table 6). Each phase has its specific objectives with phase 4 being the longest of approximately 8 years.

Table 6. TRLs in correlation to the fuel development phases [15].

TRL	Phase	Fuel Development Objectives	Time
1	1	Phase 1. Fuel candidate selection Identify fuel types and concepts with potential for meeting mission requirements.	Year 0-2
2			
3	2	Phase 2. Concept definition and feasibility Establish a reference fuel concept and design.	Year 2-10
4			
5	3	Phase 3. Fuel design improvement and evaluation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimize the reference fuel design for performance, safety and economics. Prepare a fuel specification and a licensing safety case for a reactor core of the reference fuel. Establish a predictive fuel performance code (or codes). 	Year 7-14
6			
7	4	Phase 4. Fuel qualification and demonstration <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate engineering-scale or full-scale fuel production in conformance with the fuel specification (i.e., qualify the fabrication process). Qualify production-line fuel by demonstrating fuel performance to be within the bounds of the licensing safety case. Confirm acceptable fuel behaviour under design-basis accident conditions anticipated for a licensable reactor system. Demonstrate the safety and reliability of a core or partial core of reference fuel, accumulating reactor performance data and operating experience. Validate the predictive fuel performance code or codes. 	Year 15-23

2.2.2 Accelerated approach

Looking at the timeline taken to follow the classical fuel qualification approach, it becomes clear that a change in a new paradigm is needed in order to enable timely and cost-effective commercialization of innovative nuclear fuels. There is a need to combine worldwide effort to reduce the time to qualify nuclear fuels.

The new paradigm requires a different approach to both the experimental and analytical programs, enabled by the development of a new set of tools. The new set of tools include:

- High reliability predictive modelling and simulation using multi-physics and multi-scale approach coupled with phenomenological validation over a wide range of conditions;
- Experimental capabilities for high-accuracy data collection during carefully designed in-pile and out-of-pile phenomenological experiments; and
- Micro-scale characterization and post-irradiation examination (PIE) over a large range of testing conditions, especially focusing on micro-structural phenomenology.

Therefore it is necessary to develop and demonstrate a new R&D paradigm, an Accelerated Fuel Qualification (AFQ) methodology, that shorten the fuel qualification time to less than 10 years and reduces the cost by 50% compared to the traditional process with an higher reliability, accuracy and predictability.

A resurging interest for nuclear power in the following years prompted researchers to take another look at timelines, with an interest in accelerating fuel qualification [14] [16] [17] [18] [19] [20] [21]. Identifying integral testing as the major bottleneck, a method for accelerating fuel qualification timelines based on integrating advanced modelling with separate effects testing was proposed in the manuscript [18] published under contract with the US Department of Energy (DOE). The visual illustration of the AFQ is shown in Figure 1. The proposed AFQ process consists of three phases where Phase I (basis irradiation effects and equilibrium thermodynamics) is carried on over one year followed by Phase II (integral fuel performance analysis and separate effects testing) taking up to 4 years, and Phase III (integral fuel fabrication, integral fuel irradiation and transient testing, and licensing basis) taking up to 5 years, with the total time required to have a mature fuel of ~10 years.

Figure 1. Visual workflow of AFQ process [18].

The proposal for an accelerated fuel qualification process was also put forward by NEA within Nuclear Innovation 2050 project [16] [17] as shown in Figure 2. The idea is that the principle of an optimized validation and qualification process will lead to increased efficiency and will minimize the fuel qualification time. This is a notional schedule and the exact execution depends on the success achieved in the development of predictive models and the associated experimental programs and the acceptability of the new paradigm by the safety authorities.

The TRLs 1–6 are combined into a specific “Material development and scaling” with a high focus on the predictive modelling, design envelope and fundamental properties under the normal condition as well as off-normal, transient conditions and DBA (Design Beyond Accident). The target is to reach TRL 6 in approximately 6 years. The steady state irradiation in the power plant and integral test in research reactor further cover TRLs 7–8.

Figure 2. A new paradigm for accelerating the qualification of nuclear fuels proposed by NEA [17].

A similar approach for the accelerated fuel qualification but without any specific timeline was proposed within the CONNECT-NM project with a focus on the division between modelling using Fuel Performance Codes (FPCs) and determination of materials properties [22]. The change of the paradigm in the fuel qualification process from “observe and qualify” to “design and control” was proposed by means of

- accelerated qualification of fuel performance codes, which focuses on the physics-based FPCs leveraging separate-effect validation, combination of lower-length scale analyses and database, and advanced modelling techniques always subject to integral experimental data;

- acceleration in materials properties determination, which focuses on experiment-oriented modelling and modelling-oriented experiments, fabrication and detailed characterization of samples with carefully selected and controlled compositions for ion or neutron irradiation, complementary multiscale modelling of large range of compositions and conditions, and determination of elementary mechanisms governing the behaviour from the calculations and interpretation of experiments.

This approach clearly supports the accelerated fuel qualification proposed by both DOE [18] and NEA [16] [17] as it is aligned with the need to focus on the modelling.

2.2.3 Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table Method

To accelerate fuel development, fuel system phenomena, properties, and parameters must be prioritized in respect to both the significance and the knowledge gaps of them. In addition, modelling must be integrated into experimental programs that are focused on fuel system qualification from both a design and interpretation standpoint.

The Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT) process is a systematic way of gathering information from experts on a specific concept, and ranking the importance of the information, in order to meet some decision-making objective. It has been applied to many nuclear technology issues, including nuclear analysis, to help guide research or develop regulatory requirements. The execution of the PIRT process on a specific concept is called an exercise and these exercises will vary greatly in scope and depth based on the fuel concept from the current state of practice and its maturity.

The PIRT process was developed in the late 1980s by the US Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) and its contractors to support the introduction of the best estimate plus uncertainty analysis method as a new licensing option for emergency core cooling systems in the United States [23] [24] [25].

The PIRT method requires several analysis steps as presented in [Figure 3](#) [26]. After defining all the required information from step 1 to step 6, it is equally important to define the ranking. Generally, the rank can be defined based on the “Importance Level” (IL) and “Knowledge Level” (KL) which deal with the availability of the data and the availability of the model, respectively. The definition of the importance ranks and their implications is given [Table 7](#) [27]. The knowledge level of each phenomenon with regard to both experimental data and computational models is ranked according to the three-level scale defined in [Table 8](#) [27]. The average scores for determining the importance level and knowledge level of each parameter or property are calculated by equations given in the [Table 7](#) and [Table 8](#), respectively. Finally, combined scores for each parameter or property are calculated by following equation:

$$Score = IL \times \frac{101 - KL}{100}$$

An example of results from a PIRT performed on life limiting factors (or fuel system failure) of U-Pu-Zr fuel with HT9 cladding in a sodium fast reactor [20] is shown in [Figure 4](#).

In general, the PIRT is used to assess the complete scenarios for the fuel qualification of a specific technology. However, a small PIRT assessment can be performed, such as to assess the fuel material properties for manufacturing and irradiation purposes.

Figure 3. Illustration of the PIRT process [26].

Table 7. Three-level scale used for phenomena importance ranking.

Rank	Weight	Definition	Implication
High (H)	1.0	The phenomenon has a dominant impact on any of the evaluation criteria	The phenomenon should be explicitly considered in experimental programs and modelled with high accuracy in computational tools
Medium (M)	0.5	The phenomenon has only a moderate impact on the evaluation criteria	Experimental studies and analytical modelling are required, but the scope and accuracy may be compromised
Low (L)	0.0	The phenomenon has small or no impact on the evaluation criteria	The phenomenon should be exhibited experimentally mentally and considered in computational tools. However, almost any model will be sufficient
Average score: $IL = \frac{1.0N_H + 0.5N_M + 0.0N_L}{N_H + N_M + N_L} \times 100$; where N_H , N_M and N_L are referred to the weights of “High”, “Medium” and “Low” importances, respectively.			

Table 8. Three-level scale used for ranking the current knowledge level of phenomena.

Rank	Weight	Definition - data	Definition - models
Adequate (A)	1.0	The phenomenon is well understood. Data obtained for certain conditions are available in sufficient range, quantity and quality.	Models that are validated for application to certain conditions are available.
Some (S)	0.5	Data obtained for certain conditions are available, but not in sufficient range, quantity or quality. Alternatively, data pertinent to other conditions exist and can be extrapolated to conditions in question.	The phenomenon can be approximately modelled, e.g. by lower order models or models for similar phenomena that can be extrapolated to conditions in question.
None (N)	0.0	No relevant data exist, and the phenomenon is poorly known.	No validated models exist sufficient.

Average score: $KL = \frac{1.0N_A + 0.5N_S + 0.0N_N}{N_A + N_S + N_N} \times 100$; where N_A , N_S and N_N are referred to the weights of "Adequate", "Some" and "None" knowledges, respectively

Figure 4. Final ranking results from a PIRT performed on U-Pu-Zr fuel with HT9 cladding in an SFR [20].

3. Required properties of nuclear fuels

The fuel properties are investigated as part of the fabrication process or pre-irradiation examination followed by the post-irradiation examination. To accelerate fuel development, fuel system phenomena, properties, and parameters must be prioritized in respect to both the significance of and the knowledge gaps of them. In addition, modelling must be integrated into experimental programs that are focused on fuel system qualification from

both a design and interpretation standpoint.

In order to fulfil the certain TRL of the fuel qualification, there are several precedent steps need to be taken into accounts, such as fuel fabrication, pre-irradiation examination of the fabricated fuel and post irradiation examination of the fuel irradiated under specific conditions (either via separate effect or integral irradiation) [15] [18] [28]. A typically required fuel properties for the fuel performance codes are summarized from several sources and presented in Figure 5 with some details on physical, thermophysical and mechanical properties presented in Table 9.

Figure 5. Typical properties required for innovative fuels.

Table 9. Physical, thermophysical and mechanical properties of nuclear fuels.

Physical properties	Thermophysical properties	Mechanical properties
Density	Thermal conductivity	Young's modulus
Melting temperature (solidus and liquidus)	Specific heat capacity	Poisson's ratio
Emissivity	Enthalpy	Fracture stress
Fission gas (Xe and Kr) diffusion coefficient	Thermal expansion coefficient	Hardness
Helium diffusion coefficient		Creep rate
Oxygen diffusion coefficient (high T only)		
Other properties: Lattice parameter, oxygen potential, grain properties (size, growth, etc.)		

4. Irradiation requirements

The primary safety functions of fuel are to retain all radionuclides within the fuel system to limit or prevent releases, maintain a coolable geometry, and support or not interfere with safe shutdown. A robust design, safety analysis, qualification and manufacturing process are used to produce the fuel, and strong operational oversight ensures that the fuel performs as expected.

Nuclear fuel is expected to retain its integrity under conditions of normal operation, including under the effects of anticipated operational occurrences (AOOs). Some degree of fuel failure can be accommodated for low-frequency design-basis accident (DBA) conditions which are not expected to occur during the life of the plant. The ability to achieve safe shutdown in any scenario needs to be assured. Therefore, criteria need to be established to ensure that a coolable geometry is maintained in all scenarios and that fuel system damage is never so severe as to preclude the insertion of negative reactivity sufficient to hold the reactor subcritical.

4.2 Neutron Irradiation Facility Requirements

The requirements for the neutron irradiation facilities which are mostly materials test reactors can be defined as follows:

- The facility shall allow irradiation of small-scale specimens of innovative fuel in a controlled environment so basic data on the fuel behaviour and its property evolution under irradiation can be obtained from separate effects tests. These irradiations could offer reduced cost, reduced complexity, and in the case of accelerated testing, reduced time to achieve a given burnup. Furthermore, it may be desirable to design test irradiations capable of deconvoluting the myriad effects of burnup, temperature gradients, and other factors inherent to integral irradiation tests. These irradiations are focused on mainly studies of fundamental properties and hence correspond to the TRL 4 of fuel maturity.
- The facility should allow irradiation testing of fuel performance during normal reactor operations, anticipated operational occurrences (AOOs), and design basis accidents. These irradiation testings correspond to the TRLs 5-6 of fuel maturity.
- The facility should allow irradiation testing the fuel performance in severe reactor

accidents such as a loss-of coolant accident (LOCA) and reactivity insertion accidents (RIAs). These irradiation testing correspond to the TRLs 5-6 of fuel maturity.

- The facility shall be capable of delivering fast and thermal neutron spectra comparable to commercial reactors. The irradiation experiments shall be customizable based on irradiation environment, temperature, fluence and duration. The experiment design should allow tailoring of the neutron spectrum if required.
- The research reactor shall accommodate custom-designed capsules or loops for environmental control (e.g., helium, water, sodium, lead or lead-bismuth eutectic).
- The facility shall support irradiation up to a high burnup level > 10% FIMA (Fissions per Initial Metal Atom), or as specified by the user.
- It is desirable that fuel irradiation temperature can be controllable within $\pm 50^\circ\text{C}$.
- Thermal and fast neutron flux values shall be measured and reported with <10% uncertainty.
- The facility shall support in-pile instrumentation to monitor fuel temperature (fuel centreline thermocouple), fission gas release (LVDT based fuel rod plenum pressure sensor), and dimensional changes like fuel densification/creep/swelling (LVDT based fuel stack elongation sensor), cladding elongation (LVDT based elongation detector) and diameter (LVDT based diameter gauge). In order to be able online monitoring of the neutron flux and gamma-heating, the experiments should be equipped with neutron detectors, fission chambers, gamma-detectors and neutron fluence monitors.
- The facility shall allow for post-irradiation examination (PIE) access or availability to transport the irradiated samples to partners with qualified PIE labs.

It is obvious that a single irradiation facility cannot provide entire spectrum of capabilities for irradiation testing of innovative fuel materials. Therefore, in order to perform full spectrum of innovation fuel qualification programme, several neutron irradiation facilities should be utilized.

Materials testing reactors are essential for fuel qualification, as they enable testing under representative operating conditions. However, their availability in Europe is limited. Currently, only three MTRs are in operation in Europe and capable of performing fuel testing ([Table 10](#)):

- BR2, operated by SCK CEN (Mol, Belgium),
- HFR, operated by NRG PALLAS (Petten, The Netherlands),
- CABRI (Cadarache, France).

In addition, two new research reactors are under construction:

- PALLAS, at NRG PALLAS (Petten, The Netherlands), expected in 2032;
- JHR, at CEA (Cadarache, France), expected in 2034.

Recently, nuclear fuel issues and available materials testing reactors for nuclear safety research were published by NEA [29]. The extract of the information regarding European materials testing reactors is given in [Table 10](#) and [Table 11](#). As one can observe, the capabilities for fuel irradiation testing in Europe at the present time are limited to dry irradiation at the HFR and BR2, irradiation in pressurized water capsules at BR2 and irradiation in sodium at the HFR. The use of the advanced in-pile instrumentation in these two research reactors is rather limited, in spite of the fact that the irradiation experiments equipped with fuel centreline thermocouples, LVDT based fuel rod plenum pressure sensors and LVDT based elongation detectors have been performed in the past are planned in the near future. The situation will greatly improve when PALLAS and JHR reactors will be

constructed. These two reactors will allow to perform fuel irradiation test under nominal condition of commercial reactors and also simulated accident conditions like loss-of-coolant events. The in-pile instrumentation capabilities are also envisage will be improved for studying fuel behaviour under irradiation.

Regulators and their technical support organisations, research organisations, and the industry all require F&M testing capacities on an ongoing basis. Some recent experience of test facilities attempting to re-establish prior capabilities has shown that the process can be extremely costly and time-consuming, further emphasising the importance of preserving experimental know-how through on-going research activity. In particular, the know-how and availability of test facilities for loss-of-coolant accidents, reactivity-initiated accidents and power ramps, is crucial.

Table 10. European Materials Testing Reactors capable of doing fuel irradiation tests [29].

Reactor	Type	Thermal Power (MW)	Max ther. flux (n/cm ² /s) E < 0.625 eV	Max fast flux (n/cm ² /s) E > 0.1 MeV	Irradiation capabilities/test conditions
Jules Horowitz Reactor (JHR) France	Tank in pool	100	5.5E+14	1.0E+15 5.5E+14 (E > 1 MeV)	10 in-core positions 26 reflector positions PWR water loops LOCA experiments Power ramp experiments
CABRI France	Light water pool	25 Pulse 20 GW	2.65E+13 Pulse: 2.12E+16	7.34E+13 Pulse: 5.87E+16	1 pressurised water loop (PWR, BWR, VVER) 1 channel
Belgium Reactor-2 (BR-2) Belgium	Light water tank	100	1.0E+15	7.0E+14	80 in-core channels Pressurized Water Capsule
High Flux Reactor (HFR) Netherlands	Light water tank	45	2.7E+14	5.1E+14 2.2E+14 (E > 1 MeV)	Dry irradiation Irradiation in sodium 17 in-core positions 12 out-of-core positions (Pool Side Facility – PSF)
PALLAS Netherlands	Light water pool	25	1.6E+14*	2.6E+13* (E > 1 MeV)	Multiple irradiation positions in Be reflector

*Preliminary estimations

Table 11. Current nuclear fuel issues and facilities [29].

Issues, scenarios, phenomena	Description	Facilities
Response to LOCAs	The response under LOCA conditions needs to be investigated to support development of appropriate criteria that ensure coolable geometry is maintained during and after design-basis LOCA events. Experimental data are needed, consistent with the design basis, and perhaps beyond the design-basis LOCA. Fuel fragmentation, relocation and dispersal inside the primary circuit, cooling of area with ballooning fuels have to be included in research investigations.	CABRI JHR*
Response to RIA	The response to reactivity insertion accidents needs to be investigated. Additional focus may be needed on fuel fragmentation and dispersal after boiling crisis.	CABRI
Fuel performance under steady-state conditions	The performance of new and changes in fuel and clad properties during operation can also affect the ability of the fuel to withstand design-basis accidents. Therefore, the performance of new fuel under steady-state conditions is important to ensuring the safety of operating personnel and to understanding and predicting fuel performance during design-basis accidents (i.e. the condition of the fuel and cladding resulting from steady-state operation represents the initial conditions for transients).	BR-2 HFR JHR* PALLAS*
New materials properties (fuel property database)	Improving plant performance in both existing and future plants will likely include improving fuel performance with respect to higher burnup and power levels. These improvements will require new cladding materials and the use of burnable poisons. The performance of these new materials and poisons will need verification to ensure their safety and to establish a fuel property database for safety analyses.	BR-2 HFR JHR* PALLAS*

*PALLAS and JHR are under construction and expected to be operational from 2032 and 2034, respectively.

4.3 Ion Irradiation Facility Requirements

Since the next generation nuclear power plants are generally characterized by higher operating temperatures, increased neutron fluences and energies, the fuel qualification at high burnup levels is crucial. Ion irradiation has demonstrated success in reproducing material microstructure and select property evolution resulting from neutron irradiation with three to four orders of magnitude reduction in time and cost, making it an ideal candidate for accelerated irradiation testing [30]. Because microstructure has a large impact on bulk material properties, limited neutron irradiation data at lower damage levels can in principle be combined with accelerated ion testing results and modelling and simulation to form an accurate prediction of microstructure evolution and select properties under different neutron irradiation conditions and at higher damage levels. However, there are very few

studies focusing on an approach to combine neutron and ion irradiation data to accelerate fuel material qualification [31]. This is quite obvious that ion irradiation has limited applicability to nuclear fuel, since in addition to the radiation damage, the fuel materials, in contrast to the structural materials and fuel claddings, are subjected to the fundamentally different processes under irradiation such as, for examples, generation of various gaseous and solid fission products.

The requirements for the ion irradiation facilities can be formulated as follows:

- The facility shall support multiple ion species (e.g., Kr, Xe, He) to simulate fission products and displacement damage.
- The facility shall allow dual- or triple-beam capability for synergistic irradiation effects (e.g., He and heavy ions).
- The ion energy range shall span from 100 keV to >100 MeV.
- The facility shall offer temperature control from ambient temperature to >1000°C during irradiation.
- The system shall allow micro-scale beam spot control for irradiating small fuel microstructures or thin films.
- Real-time ion flux monitoring and dose measurement shall be provided.
- Ion irradiation damage (dpa) shall be controllable and quantified with <10% uncertainty.

One of the most powerful accelerators facilities of the world capable of ion irradiation of nuclear fuel is operated by GSI Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research in Darmstadt (Germany) [32]. The facility that allows the acceleration of ions of chemical elements from proton (H) to uranium (U). The facility in-situ and online analysis techniques for characterization during irradiation UV/VIS spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, IR spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM and EDX), secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS/SNMS), etc. The ion irradiations are possible to perform under wide temperature range from 15 K to 900 K.

Furthermore, the JANNuS (Joint Accelerators for Nanosciences and Nuclear Simulation) multi-ion beam irradiation platform is the most specialized in Europe for nuclear-damage-simulation of structural / fuel-related materials, because of its triple-beam capability which emulates many relevant reactor damage mechanisms [33]. The JANNuS multi-ion beam irradiation platform was established in 2005 around two facilities: JANNuS-Orsay is located in Orsay at the Laboratoire de Physique des 2 Infinis Irène Joliot-Curie (IJCLab) and JANNuS-Saclay located on the CEA Paris-Saclay site.

The JANNuS capabilities combine a total of five electrostatic accelerators for single beam, dual beam, and triple beam ion experiments and a transmission electron microscope for in situ studies. JANNuS particle beams make it possible to irradiate small samples in a perfectly controlled manner, and thus to observe and quantify the evolution of their microstructure (segregation, precipitation, formation of dislocation loops, cavities, bubbles, etc.) and service properties. Such a scientific platform has no equivalent in Europe and plays an essential role for multi-scale modelling of radiation effects in materials.

At JANNuS-Orsay, the in situ TEM (Transmission Electron Microscopy) is can be operated in a single and dual beam modes at a chosen temperature in the range 77-1300 K, allowing in situ observation and analysis of the material microstructure modifications induced by single or dual ion irradiation.

At JANNuS-Saclay, a triple beam facility has been installed. Samples can be irradiated in the wide temperature range from liquid nitrogen (77 K) to 1000 °C. In-situ Raman spectrometry has been installed in the triple beam chamber for real time study of the

evolution of the microstructure of materials under irradiation such as to determine existing phases before and after irradiation.

Besides, the in-situ observation of the radiation damage a post-irradiation examination can also provide a valuable data through several techniques such as transmission electron microscopy (TEM), Raman spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, Rutherford backscattering spectroscopy in channelling mode (RBSC) and positron annihilation spectroscopy (PAS) [31]. Each technique brings distinct information on damage at various spatial scales (such as size and density of extended defects, level of atomic disorder, elastic strain ...). However, combining these various data to establish a scenario for the radiation damage accumulation is not always straightforward. Recently, a study of radiation defects in Xe-irradiated polycrystalline UO_2 disks has been performed using transmission electron microscopy, X-ray diffraction and positron annihilation spectroscopy characterizations [31]. The XRD provides information on elastic strain (and thus free swelling), PAS is sensitive to vacancy defects and TEM allows the direct observation of extended defects (dislocations and vacancy objects). By comparing the results provided by the these techniques, the radiation damage scenario in UO_2 was proposed.

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